

The Main Strategy of MSMEs Able to Survive in the Upcoming Latest Variant of Covid-19

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ABSTRACT

Research on the Main Strategy for MSMEs to Survive in the Face of the Latest Variants of Covid-19 in the Future is very useful research in dealing with similar problems if it happens again. This research is a qualitative research using the Netnography method with the Social Network Analysis approach through the MSME Business Actors Group on Facebook and WhatsApp. Data collection was carried out using a technical questionnaire using the Google Form application which was distributed on the MSME group's social media. The results of the study show that several strategies implemented by MSME business people have made them able to survive in the midst of a crisis storm during the Covid-19 pandemic. This research is very useful for business people and researchers in the future if there is a pandemic problem and other similar problems.

INTRODUCTION

The rediscovery of the latest variant of Covid-19 has become news that has caught the attention of the public, especially business people, including micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs). Business people from various sectors certainly cannot forget the impact of the past Covid-19 pandemic, especially the Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) policy implemented by the government. Research conducted by (Rosita, 2020) states that MSME actors have experienced a drastic decrease in income due to the implementation of physical distancing and the implementation of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB). Restricting community activities as an effort to deal with the COVID-19 pandemic has caused significant economic losses nationally (Hadiwardoyo, 2020). The government also implements a mandatory vaccine policy nationally for all people, especially those who wish to carry out external assignments such as business trips using public transportation modes such as airplanes, ships and cars as well as all users of other modes of transportation. To support the success of this government program, the majority of respondents (96.2%) of MSME business people have carried out vaccinations as a form of social responsibility, as the data is as follows:

Figure 1. Result of Respondents

The economic impact caused by the past Covid-19 Pandemic is still in the recovery period for the business world. The widespread impact of the latest variant of Covid-19, which is called the XBB variant, is a new variant of covid that originates from a mutation of the Omicron variant. The XBB variant has spread in more than 35 countries, including in Indonesia. Even though it is said to be similar to the common cold, this virus is suspected to be the culprit for the increasing cases of COVID-19 in Indonesia. This new Covid variant is a Covid Omicron variant which is not heavier than the previous variant such as Delta. The symptoms of covid XBB are also said to be similar to the previous variants. COVID-19 (Corona Virus Disaster-19) is a viral outbreak that quickly spreads to people in almost all parts of the world (Syafri, et al, 2021).

Among the many business types and forms in Indonesia, most Indonesian entrepreneurs are still at the micro and small entrepreneur level. Micro enterprises are productive businesses owned by individuals and/or individual business entities that meet the criteria for Micro Enterprises as stipulated in this Law, namely with a maximum total assets of Rp. 50,000,000, - (Fifty Million Rupiah) and the maximum turnover is Rp. 300,000,000, - (Three Hundred Million Rupiah). The research conducted (Hayati, 2021), shows that 1) there are significant differences in turnover and profit earned by MSMEs in the form of an average decrease in turnover and profit between before and during the

COVID-19 Pandemic in Kotabaru Regency, 2) MSMEs are experiencing quite a few difficulties in capital turnover, raw material supply chain and product distribution during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Kotabaru Regency. Indonesia, which is dominated by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), needs to pay special attention to this sector because the contribution of MSMEs to the national economy is quite large (Nalini, 2021).

To anticipate the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, business players, including MSME entrepreneurs, need to prepare several strategies. The research conducted (Sari et al, 2021) recommends that the MSMEs survival strategy is to trade through e-commerce and optimize marketing relationships with consumers, and maintain products and take care of existing customers. Research conducted (Liza, et al, 2022), concluded that maintaining the continuity of small businesses (MSMEs) by utilizing the internet and social media is a very appropriate strategy in the midst of the co-19 pandemic. Other researchers (Firdaus, 2021) say that Product Innovation and Development, carry out product marketing with digital marketing, carry out customer relationship marketing (customer relationship marketing) to create consumer trust and grow customer loyalty. Research (Ihza, 2020) recommends that the MSME survival strategy is to trade through e-commerce, digital marketing, adding services to consumers and optimizing marketing relationships with consumers, and maintaining products and maintaining customers.

The results of the study (Hardilawati, 2020), recommend a survival strategy for MSME in the form of conducting e-commerce trade, conducting digital marketing, improving product quality and adding services as well as establishing and optimizing customer marketing relationships. Research (Melinda, 2021), states as follows that the first is to take advantage of the positive side of technology to disseminate products and the second is to reduce prices. The results of the study (Nawawi, 2021), show that MSME actors must implement new business strategies amid the covid-19 pandemic. There are various business strategies that can be used, namely improving the quality of products and services, digital entrepreneurship and customer relationship marketing.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Strategy

Strategy is a long-term plan that is structured to deliver to an achievement of certain goals and objectives. The word strategy comes from the word Strategos in Greek which is a combination of Stratos or army and ego or leader. A strategy has a basis or scheme to achieve the intended goal. So basically strategy is a tool to achieve goals. According to David (2004) strategy is a unified, broad and integrated plan that links a company's strategic advantages with environmental challenges, designed to ensure that the main goals of the company can be achieved through proper implementation by the organization.

Main strategies often called master strategies or business strategies, provide basic direction for strategic actions. The emergence of business interruptions that affect the company needs to be handled swiftly to avoid

financial losses. This response is very necessary to ensure business continuity in the future. However, all elements of the business need to be evaluated and protected in advance with an on going plan. A survival strategy needs to be carried out in dealing with new conditions during the Covid-19 Pandemic, what is meant is by carrying out a plan by an individual or group in obtaining the desired goals and solving a problem faced, in this case it can be in the form of actions or action. (Alfin, 2021).

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)

In Article 1 Number 20 of 2008 defines MSMEs as (1) Micro businesses are businesses in the economic sector owned by individuals who meet the requirements and criteria for MSMEs regulated in the Law. (2) Small business is a business in the economic sector which is self-established either as an individual or as a business entity where this small business is not part of a branch of medium or large business in terms of ownership, power, or being a part directly or indirectly according to the criteria for small business regulated in the Act. (3) Medium-sized business is a business in the economic sector that is self-established either as an individual or as a business entity where this medium-sized business is not part of a branch of small business or large business in terms of ownership, power, or being a part directly or indirectly according to the criteria for medium-sized business. which are regulated in the Law (Utami, 2021).

According to Law of the Republic of Indonesia No.20 of 2008 concerning MSMEs. Article 1 of the Law states that a micro business is a productive business owned by an individual or individual business entity which has criteria for micro businesses as regulated in the Law (Khusna, 2021). Based on Law Number 20 of 2008, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are a type of small business that has a maximum net worth of IDR. 200,000,000 excluding land and buildings where the business is located. and stand-alone businesses (Alfin, 2021).

Covid-19

Covid-19 is a new outbreak that emerged at the end of 2019. This outbreak first originated in Wuhan, China. This outbreak is a very dangerous virus because the virus is invisible and can kill many people. The existence of this virus not only has an impact on health, but also on several sectors throughout the world (Ihza, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic has changed many human behaviors. Corona virus disease (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. COVID-19 (Corona Virus Disaster-19) is a virus outbreak that is rapidly spreading to people in almost all parts of the world. Currently, deaths caused by COVID-19 have reached thousands of people worldwide. Indonesia itself is inseparable from this deadly virus (Syaffitri, 2022). This deadly virus makes changes to everyday human behavior. Deaths caused by COVID-19 occurred massively in many countries, including Indonesia (Syafri, 2021).

The world seems to be rapidly changing in various areas of human life, such as the closure of large stores, shopping centers, malls, supermarkets, and so on, changing people's shopping behavior by switching to using online media. Many shops, shopping centers, malls and supermarkets are experiencing bankruptcy due to changes in people's shopping behavior using online media. This provides new opportunities for online shops, Marketplaces, Company Websites to get a large overflow of turnover with changes in shopping behavior (Syafiril, et al, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

This research is a qualitative research with a netnography method approach and social network analysis, namely network-based research. Netnography is a research method for understanding the interaction of society and culture formed through networks. During the pandemic, netnography was suitable for research to find out the phenomena at that time, namely social media used for business. This research collects data from questionnaires using the Google form application which is distributed to various MSME groups on Facebook and WhatsApp.

RESEARCH RESULT

From the results of the questionnaire distributed through the Google form application, various demographic data were obtained from MSME actors, as the data description is as follows:

Table 1. Result MSME

Gender:	
Man	38.5%
Woman	61.5%
Respondent Age:	
17 to 28 years	11.5%
29 to 40 years	30.8%
41 to 50 years	42.2%
51 to 60 years	15.5%
Last education:	
SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	34.6%
Bachelor degree (S1)	38.5%
Masters (S2)	28.9%

From the demographic data above, it can be concluded that most of the MSME business actors in this survey were female as many as 16 respondents (61.5%) and were dominantly aged over 40 years to 50 years (42.2%), while education was the most the lowest number of respondents were high school graduates with the equivalent of 9 respondents (38.2%), Bachelor graduates (S1) of 10 respondents (38.5%) and followed by Masters graduates (S2) of 7 respondents (28.9%).

From the results of the questionnaires given, it is known that most MSME business people earn an average monthly income of IDR 1,000,000-<Rp.

5,000,000 which is the income of 20 respondents (76.9%) and IDR 5,000,000- <10,000,000 as many as 4 respondents (15.4%). This shows that the income as a MSMEs business player is enough to help their family's economy. This can be seen from the diagram below as follows:

Diagram 1. Results of the Questionnaires

Another interesting thing from the results of the questionnaire survey submitted to respondents is that MSME business people still have other jobs, either as their main job or side job. From the diagram shown below it is known that their profession has the status of Civil Servants (PNS) as much as 1 respondent (3.8%), Contract Employees (PPPK) as many as 4 respondents (15.4%) and private company employees as many as 6 people (38.5%). The data in the diagram below is as follows:

Diagram 2. MSME Business

Strategies Of MSME Business Players

From several strategies carried out by MSME business respondents during the Covid-19 pandemic, it can be used as a guide in dealing with the same problems in the future with various considerations and improvements so that MSME business actors can still survive. Some of the strategies carried out as examples of respondents' answers below are as follows:

Table 2. Strategies Of MSME Business Players

Strategies Implemented by MSME Business Actors	Not Doing Strategy	Netral	Doing Strategy
During the Covid-19 Pandemic I sold on e-commerce platforms such as Lazada, Matahari Mall, and so on	9 (34.6%)	6 (23,1%)	11 (42,3%)
During the Covid-19 Pandemic I only sold part time or half a day, day or night	8 (30,9%)	7 (26,9%)	11 (42,3%)

During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business was only open on certain days, not every day	12 (46,2%)	6 (23,1%)	8 (30,9%)
During the Covid-19 Pandemic I opened a business online through available online business applications	5 (19,2%)	7 (26,9%)	14 (53,8%)
During the Covid-19 Pandemic I only served customer orders directly from my home and place of business	8 (30,9%)	4 (15,4%)	14 (53,8%)
During the Covid-19 Pandemic I collaborated with online motorcycle taxis in marketing my products, such as GrabFood, etc	10 (38,5%)	8 (30,9%)	8 (30,9%)
During the Covid -19 Pandemic I increased the value and quality of my products	2 (7,7%)	9 (34,6%)	15 (57,7%)
During the Covid-19 Pandemic I only served my regular customer orders	12 (46,2%)	9 (34,6%)	5 (19,2%)
During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business was closed	17 (65,4%)	5 (19,2%)	4 (15,4%)
During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business income was reduced than usual	4 (15,4%)	7 (26,9%)	15 (57,7%)
During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business income increased from usual	15 (57,7%)	7 (26,9%)	4 (15,4%)
During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business was still running as usual	6 (23,1%)	8 (30,9%)	12 (46,2%)

DISCUSSION

From the results of the questionnaire given, it can be concluded that there is an overview of several strategies carried out by MSME business actors to survive the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic that hit at that time and there is a possibility that this could happen again in Indonesia. The strategy for MSME business actors to be able to survive during the Covid-19 pandemic can be explained in the perimeter as follows:

- 1) During the Covid-19 Pandemic I sold on e-commerce platforms such as Lazada, Matahari Mall, and so on. This strategy was carried out by 11 (42.3%) respondents and 6 (23.1%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, 9 (34.6%) respondents did not use this strategy.
- 2) During the Covid-19 Pandemic I only sold part time or half the day, day or night. This strategy was carried out by 11 (42.3%) respondents and 7 (26.9%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, there were 8 (30.9%) respondents who did not use this strategy.
- 3) During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business was only open on certain days, not every day. This strategy was carried out by 8 (30.9%) respondents and 6 (23.1%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, 12 respondents (46.2%) did not use this strategy
- 4) During the Covid-19 Pandemic I opened a business online through available online business applications. This strategy was carried out by

- 14 (53.8%) respondents and 7 (26.9%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, 5 (19.2%) respondents did not use this strategy.
- 5) During the Covid-19 Pandemic I only served customer orders directly from homes and places of business. This strategy was carried out by 14 (53.8%) respondents and 4 (15.4%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, there were 8 (30.9%) respondents who did not use this strategy.
 - 6) During the Covid-19 Pandemic I collaborated with online motorcycle taxis in marketing my products, such as GrabFood, etc. This strategy was carried out by 8 (30.9%) respondents and 8 (30.9%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, 10 respondents (38.5%) did not use this strategy
 - 7) During the Covid -19 Pandemic I increased the value and quality of my products. This strategy was carried out by 15 (57.7%) respondents and 9 (34.6%) respondents answered Neutral. While the respondents who did not use this strategy were 2 (7.7%) respondents.
 - 8) During the Covid-19 Pandemic I only served my regular customer orders. This strategy was carried out by 5 (19.2%) respondents and 9 (34.6%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, 12 respondents (46.2%) did not use this strategy.
 - 9) During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business was completely closed. This strategy was carried out by 4 (15.4%) respondents and 5 (19.2%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, 17 respondents (65.4%) did not use this strategy.
 - 10) During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business income was reduced than usual. This strategy was carried out by 15 (57.7%) respondents and 7 (26.9%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, there were 4 (15.4%) respondents who did not use this strategy.
 - 11) During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business income increased from usual. . This strategy was carried out by 4 (15.4) respondents and 7 (26.9%) respondents answered Neutral. Meanwhile, 15 (57.7%) respondents did not do this strategy.

During the Covid-19 Pandemic my business was still running as usual. This strategy was carried out by 12 (46.2%) respondents and 8 (30.9%) respondents answered Neutral. While respondents who did not use this strategy were 6 (23.1%) respondents.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the several strategies carried out by MSME business actors, it can be concluded that the strategy is selling on e-commerce platforms, selling part time, opening only on certain days, opening businesses online through available online business applications, serving customer orders directly. from homes and places of business, collaboration with online motorcycle taxis in marketing products, increasing product value and quality, and business is still running as usual. The strategies above are the main strategies that many MSME business people carried out during the past Covid-19 pandemic.

Another strategy that is no less important is carried out by MSME business actors, including not only serving regular customer orders, not completely closing the business, and agreeing that their income has decreased compared to usual. The strategies undertaken will certainly have an impact on the business development of the next MSME business actors. Several strategies during the past Covid-19 pandemic are certainly still relevant to be applied if this incident occurs again in the future.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic "The Main Strategy of MSMEs Able to Survive in the Upcoming Latest Variant of Covid-19" to perfect this research, as well as increase insight for readers.

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